

CEDA climate data: communicating about complex services

Authors:

Poppy Townsend ^{1,2}

Affiliations:

- 1 - NERC Environmental Data Service
- 2 - Science and Technology Facilities Council

Contents

About this work	3
Summary	3
Rationale for the work	3
Methodology	4
Lessons learnt	4
Opportunities and future recommendations	4

About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This work has looked at improving the way in which the range of CEDA's data holdings and services can be communicated to existing and potential new users. It has focussed on creating a light-touch quick start guide, which links with more detailed existing help pages.

It focuses on CEDA's rendition of Ed Hawkins' world-famous climate warming stripes as a way of illustrating the data and services, this work recognises that CEDA's target audience covers a wide spectrum of interests, disciplines, and technical abilities

Rationale for the work

The contents of CEDA's data archive have grown enormously over its 30 year life span.

- This can make it potentially difficult for users to find the datasets that are likely to be of most use to them.
- Some of the people responsible for providing and archiving the data have moved on to different roles or retired.
- The use of data across traditional discipline boundaries has increased during the last 30 years and so the target audience is less clearly defined.
- Data standards, archiving conventions, and the way in which datasets are "advertised" have all evolved over 30 years, CEDA's holdings are therefore somewhat inhomogeneous.
- Long-standing users of CEDA may be unaware of new datasets that have been added to the archive and of the improved ways of discovering and accessing them.

CEDA has created almost 100 help pages for users of the archive

- These are better suited to users who already know what they are looking for than for new users.

- Some of these pages contain out-of-date information and broken links

Methodology

The work was primarily carried out by someone whose main experience of the CEDA Archive has been as a data provider rather than as a data user or as a core member of the CEDA team.

This was a deliberate decision aimed at discovering how easy it was to discover the data are services based purely on the information already available.

The main aim of the work was to create a quick start guide to provide basic (rather than detailed) information on how to:

- Discover potentially useful datasets
- Determine if a dataset is appropriate for an intended purpose
- Access the data files
- Benefit from CEDA's tools and services

Other aims of the work were to:

- Review the existing help pages and record instances of out-of-date information and broken links
- Link to the existing help pages from the quick start guide

Lessons learnt

- The CEDA Archive and the “catalogue pages” that describe datasets can be discovered and accessed in multiple ways (there is no single way)
- More needs to be done to ensure that the appropriate help resources are visible irrespective of the route that users follow. The catalogue pages present a homogeneous interface to datasets that can be quite varied in other ways (this is a good thing)
- The more modern datasets have benefitted from the evolution of widely-used data standards, which make them technically easier to access and scientifically easier to understand (these are good things)

Opportunities and future recommendations

- The quick start guide should be integrated into the existing help pages and made prominent and accessible for all.
- It would be good to get feedback from a wider cross-section of users on how they navigate the CEDA systems, what they find easy, and what they have had difficulties with.